

NEOSUCCESS

 Ref. Ares(2020)4337856 - 20/08/2020

Upscaling and Market Introduction of
Simultaneous Biogas Upgrading and Bio-
Succinic Acid Production

D6.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

NEOSUCCESS Project
Grant Agreement No. 950921

DOCUMENT TYPE (R/DEM/DEC/OTHER)
DEC _ WEBSITES, PATENTS FILLINGS, ETC.

DISSEMINATION LEVEL (PU/CO/CI)
PU_ PUBLIC

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V1	04/08/2020	Dates stated in the Grant Agreement	Goar W. Ramírez (IVEM)

Additional author(s) and contribution	
Name	Organisation

Document distribution		
Issue	Date	Distributed to

Verification and approval		
	Date	Name
Verification final Draft by WP leader (NORVENTO)	18/08/2020	Javier Taibo Pose
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator (IVEM)	18/08/2020	Francisco Heredia

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 950921”

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 950921

Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION	5
1.1	THE NEOSUCCESS PROJECT	5
1.2	THE WEBPAGE	5
2	WEBPAGE CONTENT, STRUCTURE AND LAYOUT	6
2.1	MENTION TO FUNDING BODIES	7
2.2	HOMEPAGE.....	7
2.3	THE PROJECT	8
2.4	PARTNERS.....	9
2.5	DOCUMENTS	10
2.6	LINKS.....	10
2.7	AGENDA.....	11
2.8	NEWSLETTER	11
2.9	CONTACT	12
3	FOLLOWING STEPS	12

Executive Summary

The Deliverable D6.1, referred to the project website, belongs to the Work Package 6 “Dissemination and Communication” (M1-M36) and is part of the Task 6.1 – Dissemination and Communication (D&C), led both by NORVENTO.

The main objective of this deliverable is to give an overview of the project website, which was specifically designed for the project and aims at disseminating the advances and results obtained within among the public and potential users. This website will be nonetheless updated along the implementation of the project with the main outcomes.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 THE NEOSUCCESS PROJECT

The project NEOSUCCESS aims at building a containerized and plug-and-play solution to be implemented at industrial scale to simultaneously compile two different and complex processes, such as i) biogas upgrading to biomethane and ii) biosuccinic acid (bioSA) production. In this regard, NEOSUCCESS solution is based on a patented technology by DTU (also partner of the present project), whose application relies on the fermentation of sugars in the presence of CO₂ by a specific bacteria, *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, under anaerobic conditions.

The two abovementioned bio-based products, biomethane and bioSA, are of key relevance for the energy and chemical industries, since they are potential substitutes for natural gas and petroleum-based succinic acid, respectively. The interest on this technology relies not only on its cost-efficiency, but also on the environmental benefits associated to it (basically due to the reduced CO₂ emissions) compared to conventional technologies devoted to the production of these bio-based products. In this sense, it must be stressed that the technology addresses climate actions in line with the Paris Agreement and, most importantly, with the current European Green Deal commitments.

Since the technology has been proved at lab- and pilot-scale, this Fast-Track-to-Innovation (FTI) project has the objective of not only building the industrial unit, but also of validating it in a real environment to reach the market readiness expected by the end of the project (TRL 6→TRL9). To this aim, the creation of an adequate dissemination and communication plan is crucial to create a potential client's network and consequently ensure a rapid market uptake.

1.2 THE WEBPAGE

The webpage of the NEOSUCCESS project is one of the most important online channels for D&C actions. The webpage was published on M3 of the project and is accessible by any visitor:

1. It provides information on the project, public results and contacts of the main entities involved.
2. It allows to download newsletters and public dissemination documents of interest for different audiences, including targeted stakeholders.
3. The project webpage will be promoted by all partners involved. Project partners will link the project web from their organization's websites to improve the SEO positioning of the domain as well as the visibility and the impact of the NEOSUCCESS project.

2 WEBPAGE CONTENT, STRUCTURE AND LAYOUT

The NEOSUCCESS website was officially launched on 01/08/2020 at the URL www.neosuccess-project.eu according to DoA specifications and the expected chronogram of the current project. The contents of this first version of the webpage are available in English, though by the end of the project will be also in Spanish and a third language (which will depend on the target countries selected later on in the business plan). The webpage counts with the following sections (**Fig. 1**):

- The Project
- Partners
- Documents
- Links
- Agenda
- Newsletter
- Contact

Figure 1. Upper part of the homepage of NEOSUCCESS project website.

The structure of the website was chosen aiming at acquiring the desired level of functionality, thus allowing visitors to easily navigate it to access any information required about NEOSUCCESS. The section “The Project” is addressed to general public with more general information regarding the project, while the remaining sections are addressed to a more technical audience (especially the section “Documents” and “Agenda”).

Footer and header areas containing horizontal main menu bars constitute the general layout of the webpage, thus presenting links to the sections abovementioned.

The NEOSUCCESS logo is displayed in the left side of the header and loads the homepage once it is clicked. The header also includes a “search function” to retrieve specific

contents within the webpage, and a “more information function” to load the latest entries and comments of the “Agenda” section.

Figure 2 show the layout of the header of the webpage.

Figure 2. Header of the NEOSUCCESS website.

On the other hand, links to the “search function” and the entries regarding news and events from “Agenda” are available within the footer. Finally, links to the social media channels listed in the D&C Plan (see D6.2 for more details) are also available at the bottom of the footer.

The different sections of the webpage will be hereafter briefly presented, including pictures to make it clearer.

2.1 MENTION TO FUNDING BODIES

The footer of the NEOSUCCESS webpage includes the H2020 logo and the corresponding acknowledgment of the EU funding (“*This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 950921*”) The footer is visible in all pages of the webpage.

Figure 3. Footer of the NEOSUCCESS website.

2.2 HOMEPAGE

The central homepage of NEOSUCCESS counts with three different sections, which are welcome, international collaboration and EU support (Fig. 4). The first two sections include links to the corresponding supporting pages, “The Project” and “Partners”, where a wider description of the project and the entities involved is given, respectively. Additionally, a link to the “Contact” section is provided below the EU support subsection to enable the reader to rapidly ask for more information to the coordinator, if required.

Finally, as other sections within the webpage, footer and header are present within the homepage as previously described.

Figure 4. Homepage of NEOSUCCESS website.

2.3 THE PROJECT

“The Project” section contains a more detailed description of the project compared to the homepage, and it is divided into four different subpages with the following structure:

- Description – it details both in text and figure the most important data regarding the technology employed, the scale and figures expected (**Fig. 5**). Also, it summarizes the main advantages of the NEOSUCCESS technology, which make it competitive over other technologies of biogas upgrading and succinic acid production.
- Objectives – it provides information regarding the overall objective of the current project and divides it into different technical and commercial objectives according to the typology of the project and the actions described in the DoA.
- Activities – it summarizes the strategy of the project with a description of the six work packages (WPs) within. The information is supported with a representative figure interlinking the WPs.
- Results – it describes the main outcomes expected along the NEOSUCCESS project.

Figure 5. Description subsection within NEOSUCCESS website.

2.4 PARTNERS

This section presents the partners of the consortium responsible for NEOSUCCESS. Each partner is listed with its logo and a link to its own webpage. A description of the main activities of each partner is underneath included. An example of the description of IVEM, the coordinator, is given in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Partners section within NEOSUCCESS website.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 950921

2.5 DOCUMENTS

The section “Documents” includes public documents of the project susceptible to being downloaded as PDF (**Fig. 7**). The documents will be available in four different subsections, which are Executive Summary, Press Releases, Public Deliverable Reports, Public Dissemination Activities.

Figure 7. Documents section within NEOSUCCESS website.

2.6 LINKS

This section of the website includes links of interest related to the NEOSUCCESS project, such as those of the Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC), the EU bioeconomy strategy portal or the European Commission (Energy subsection) (**Fig. 8**).

Figure 8. Links section within NEOSUCCESS website.

2.7 AGENDA

The section “Agenda” includes information regarding news and events of NEOSUCCESS project in a blog format. Tags for each type of entry and comment and like tools are also available in this section (**Fig. 9**).

Figure 9. Agenda section within NEOSUCCESS website.

2.8 NEWSLETTER

In this section anybody interested in the project can register for the NEOSUCCESS newsletters and, thus, regularly receive information regarding advances on it (**Fig. 10**). The section is currently under construction and will be ready before the creation of the first newsletter in M6.

Figure 10. Newsletter section within NEOSUCCESS website.

2.9 CONTACT

This section enables visitors to contact the project coordinator (IVEM) using the contact details available (**Fig. 11**).

Figure 11. Contact section within NEOSUCCESS website.

3 FOLLOWING STEPS

The following steps regarding the adequation and/or management of the webpage involve:

- Creation of hyperlinks to the corresponding social media channels, once created.
- Upload of public documents and news related to the project in the sections “Documents” and “Agenda”, respectively.
- Translation of the webpage to Spanish and the third language (if applicable) along the project execution, according to the DoA.